

Development of a HF Broadcast Simulator for Whole Aircraft Testing

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Abstract: Worldwide, High frequency (HF) broadcaster radiates very high intensity radiated fields in the airspace used by both civil and military aircraft. Testing of aircraft at the Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division, Patuxent River Maryland is performed to determine the compatibility with the external electromagnetic environment. The Office of Secretary of Defense (OSD) Central Test and Evaluation Investment Program (CTEIP) recognized the need for aircraft to be electro magnetically compatible with the HF broadcast electromagnetic environment (EME) CTEIP has supported the development of a new simulator that permits aircraft to be tested for compatibility with the EME produce by HF broadcast. This paper will describe the validation of these fields, the antenna development, transmitter capabilities and resulting whole radiated fields for aircraft testing.

Introduction

The Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division at Patuxent River Maryland (NAVAIRWARCENACDIV) operates ground test facilities to test aircraft to simulated high intensity radiate fields that aircraft could encounter worldwide. In 1987 the Electromagnetic Environment Generating System (EMEGS) was completed. EMEGS is capable of simulating the shipboard EME for Naval Aircraft. The HF environment aboard ships is the severest when the aircraft is parked over the top of a deck edge horizontal 35 foot whip antenna. The field in this configuration could be as high as 200 v/m. The laboratory EMEGS simulation uses a 35 foot vertical whip, 10 feet from the aircraft.

The electromagnetic environment encountered by civil aircraft flying by HF broadcast is documented in reference [1]. A civil aircraft is allowed to be in the range of 100 to 1000 feet from the HF broadcast antenna where the field is 200-300 v/m. The environment encountered by aircraft at 100 to 1000 feet above HF Broadcast systems is not accurately simulated by the shipboard HF simulation provided by the EMEGS the ground test facilities. This T&E capability short fall for

a major worldwide EME emitter resulted in the Office of Secretary of Defense Central Test and Evaluation Investment Program funding the development of a HF Broadcast Simulator System (HFBSS). The goals of the HFBSS are as follows.

- To provide simulation of the worldwide HF broadcast EME seen by both fixed wing and rotorcraft.
- To illuminate the whole aircraft with the HF EME.
- To be able to test the aircraft with engine operating, and propeller and rotor blades turning.
- To be compatible with exiting T&E facilities.

Validation

The first step in developing the HFBSS was to better understand the commercial HF Broadcast RF facilities and it's interaction with aircraft. A field visit was made to a HF broadcast facility at Greenville North Carolina, which radiates Voice of America (VOA) Programming to Africa and Eastern Europe. There are in fact three operational sites situated in the countryside near the Greenville Commercial Airport. Each site consists of several 500 KW 6-23 MHz transmitters that can be routed by open balanced transmission line to numerous antenna sites. The antennas are large phased array antennas with rear reflectors that radiate horizontally. Depending upon the target audience they steer and focus the beam antenna beam by emitting on 1 or all of the folded dipole elements in the antenna array.

Figure 1 is typical of the antenna analyzed in reference [1] as producing the highest field for airborne aircraft. The physical and electrical characteristics were gathered during the field visit and fed to a NEC method-of-moments model of the antenna. The modeled field plots confirmed the field intensities and gave a good picture of what the illumination was like.

Further investigation revealed that 4-6 MHz is reserved for subtropical broadcasting and 23 to 26 MHz is used for point-to-point broadcast links. Vertical polarization would be used anywhere in the HF band for point-to-point broadcast links or communications using a log periodic antenna.

Figure 1. HF Curtain Array Antenna

All of this information was then analyzed to determine the best way to proceed to simulate the EME in the laboratory for ground testing of aircraft.

The concept system that resulted from the HF broadcast validation was to use an off-the-shelf commercial HF transmitter and a custom antenna.

Antenna

The antenna development was started first. It became obvious after talking with the HF broadcasters and HF broadcast antenna manufactures that HF antennas, despite them being listed in catalogs, are all custom items. The requirement to radiate a field to an aircraft on the ground instead of to countries on distant continents further complicated the situation. The specifications listed in table 1 were used to describe the concept antenna system requirements. The antenna had to be broadbanded to radiate over the entire HF broadcast band of 3.9 to 26 MHz, special emphasis was placed on the authorized frequencies used at Patuxent

River, MD. Both vertical and horizontal polarizations were needed to be seen by the aircraft under test simulating the broadcast polarization or aircraft geometry. Unbalanced 75 ohm, 9 inch coax was selected for the transmission line due to it safety to personnel, ease of setup, high power rating, no pressurization requirements and no spurious signal leakage. The sizes of aircraft was described as small as a T-45 Goshawk trainer to as large as a Boeing 747 Wide body Transport Aircraft or an AH-1W Cobra Attack Helicopter to a CH-53 Sea King Cargo Helicopter. Given the large variation in aircraft, the illumination area was to be as large and uniform as practical and still result in a 200 to 300 V/m field.

The HFBSS was primarily to be setup at the airfield on board NAVAIRWARCENACDIV, Patuxent River; however, it was required to be setup anywhere in the United States. The HFBSS has to be transportable over normal highways and modular to allow rapid relocation and setup. If the antenna had to have guy wired the guy wires could not interfere with engine, propeller and rotor blade operation. The height of the antenna had to be compatible with airport height restriction.

These specifications were released to HF broadcast antenna industry with the request for someone to study the requirements and recommend a suitable design.

There were 4 bidders to the request for proposals. Two study contracts were awarded to conceive the custom HF antenna. This approach fostered competition and gave more than one antenna design to pick from for fabrication. One contact award was made to Technology Communication International (TCI) from Fremont California; who has made a majority of the HF antennas used by VOA. The other contract award went to Antenna Products from Mineral Wells Texas, a provider of numerous specialty Low Frequency to HF high power antennas. These two companies independently researched approaches to designing an antenna that met the requirements.

Table 1 HFBSS Antenna Specification

1. **Frequency Range.** The antenna shall be capable of operating over the HF frequency range of 3.9 MHz to 26 MHz continuously. The primary frequencies authorized of HF broadcast are 4.04, 4.805, 5.385, 6.4, 6.97, 7.99, 9.05, 9.803, 11.0645, 12.045, 13.53, 16.06, 17.048, 18.036, 19.27, 20.51, 21.46, 23.18, and 24.45 MHz.
2. **Polarization.** The antenna shall radiate fields that result in either a horizontally or vertically polarized fields in the illumination volume. The polarization may be selectable by reconfiguring a single set of radiating elements, and/or by reconfiguring the transmission system.
3. **Transmission Line.** The transmitter and antenna shall be connected with 75 ohm 9 inch coaxial transmission line. The transmission line between the antenna and the transmitter external output are part of the antenna system.
4. **Illumination Volume.** It is desired to radiate aircraft that range in size from a T-45 Goshawk up to a Boeing 747-400 (fixed wing aircraft), and a AH-1W up to a CH-53 (rotary wing aircraft).
5. **Electric Field Intensity.** The aircraft illumination volume shall have fields of 200 V/M rms for fixed wing aircraft and 300 V/M rms for rotary wing aircraft (the fields are based on CW transmissions). The fields must be as uniform as practicable. The distance from the antenna to the illumination volume or the transmitter output power may be adjusted as necessary to achieve the desired electric field intensity and optimum field uniformity.
6. **Environment.** The primary site of the antenna system is the NAVAIRWARCENACDIV, Patuxent River, Maryland; however, provision should be considered to allow transport and operation anywhere in the contiguous 48 United States.
7. **Physical Location** The antenna system will be located on the East side of the NAVAIRWARCENACDIV Patuxent River Naval Electromagnetic Radiation Facility (NERF)
8. **Guy Wires.** The antenna system shall not require any guy wires or ground securing attachments outside the primary footprint of the antenna. Guy wire shall not interfere with aircraft engine or rotor blade operation at the NERF. **Size.** The height of the antenna must be compatible with the airport height restrictions for the location cited in section 8 above. The antenna width, depth, and footprint must be compatible with the available space at NERF
10. **Transportability.** The antenna system will be primarily a fixed installation on the east side of the NERF. However, the antenna must be capable of being relocated to other locations near the NERF or within the contiguous 48 United States. The relocation shall have goal of less than two week each to configure for transportation or re-assembly at the new location (transit time not included). The new location may require unique facilities to accommodate the antenna assembly. The time need to

obtain these facilities would not be included in the time period.

The hardest requirement both encountered was creating a horizontal field to aircraft parked on the ground. Maxwell's equations for a horizontal field require the field to go to zero at the ground plane and a maximum at a quarter-wave above the ground. This meant for a typical dipole curtain array the field maximum would be 35 feet about the ground and zero on the ground. The field was good for large aircraft, but not for small aircraft. Many concepts were looked at including a parabolic reflector, folded dipole arrays, and ground current cancellation. The studies concluded with the contractors providing a final report with their recommended best approach to meeting the requirements. These reports were used as the proposals for award of the best design for fabrication.

Figure 2 V Dipole Curtain

The winning design was a V dipole curtain from TCI. The antenna consists of two triangular trusses suspended at 45 degrees from the ground and 90 degrees from each other, figure 2. The antenna is mounted on an 8 foot wide by 50 foot flat bed trailer. Behind the antenna is a matching network trailer on a similar trailer. In the vertical mode, the matching network trailer takes the 75 ohm unbalanced output from the transmitter and makes impedance match to feed the two antenna elements in phase. In the horizontal mode, the matching network connect the 75 ohm unbalanced output to a balun, then to the matching network which feed the two antenna elements out of phase. Further behind the matching network trailer is the 100 foot wide curtain. It consists of 4 trailers, each with a mast and catenaries to support a 25 foot wide by 80 feet high section of the curtain. The field plots were developed using a TCI finite element

proprietary code, developed for the HF Broadcast industry. In the vertical polarization, the field is very uniform as can be seen in the centerline and 6 foot high horizontal cut of figures 3 and 4. In the horizontal polarizations the design concept used to counter Maxwell (ground plane effects) was to lower the antenna as close to the ground a practical. The horizontal field center cut, figure 5 shows the concentration of the field, with a significant uniform field down low where the small aircraft would be. The 6 foot high horizontal cut, figure 6 show a usable field up close to the antenna. The TCI design provided the optimum field illumination while meeting the portability and cost goals of the program.

Figure 3 Vertical Polarization, Centerline Vertical Cross Section

Figure 4 Vertical Polarization, 6 Foot Elevation Horizontal Cross Section

Figure 5 Horizontal Polarization, Vertical Centerline Cross Section

Figure 6 Horizontal Polarization, 6 Foot Elevation Horizontal Cross Section

Transmitter

The transmitter is an off the shelf commercial HF broadcast transmitter from Continental Electronics Corporation from Dallas Texas. The transmitter outputs 300 kW CW and in normal AM modulation is capable of peak amplitudes 12000 kW. The transmitter is built to take a 500 kW tube from either CPI, Semains or Thompson. The modulator is designed using a class D amplifier. There are 48 programmable high voltage power supplies whose output levels follows the amplitude of the incoming modulation. Minor voltage steps are smoothed with integrating capacitors. This results in a very efficient design because, when there is no modulation present the transmitter has no high voltage applied, consuming minimal power and yet can put out maximum output with the next instant of audio program. Furthermore, with so many power supplies, it is possible for one or more of the supplies to malfunction and the transmitter keep functioning at full or near full capacity. The transmitter is outfitted to provide voice,

music and steady tone audio programming in AM and single side band transmission.

The antenna system consist of 6 trailers. There are three more to comprise the total HFBS system. The transmitter component adds two more trailers. The transmitter was integrated into a 14 foot wide by 50 foot long enclosed trailer called the Transportable Transmitter Enclosure (TTE). The cooling equipment and dummy load was placed on a second 8 foot wide, 50 foot long flat bed trailer. The TTE takes an input supply voltage of 4160 volts and transforms it to all other voltages necessary to service the transmitter, cooling equipment and dummy load cooling. The 4160 volts is supplied by the last trailer, which is an 800 KW, 4.16 KV diesel generator, with an 8 hour fuel tank.

Dummy Load

The dummy load that is on the cooling trailer is a 500 KW dummy load with integral calorimeter function. It uses an air cooled tapered resistive line. This dummy load is a major advance in high power loads. Traditional high power loads are liquid sodium systems that circulate the hot conductive liquid over the RF electrodes. The air-cooled load avoided the complication of maintaining the liquid's electrical properties (temperature and concentration) and avoids the corrosiveness of the salts.

Status

The status of the HFBSS as of this paper is as follows.

- The antenna has completed fabrication, factory checkout and is being integrated with the transmitter at Patuxent River. The transmitter integration include field measurements and high power operational check.
- The CEC Transmitter was received at Patuxent River in August 2000. The transmitter integration was delayed until March 2001 due to delays with the antenna and generator delivery.
- The 4160 Volt/800 Kw generator was received at Patuxent River in early March. Immediately afterward the integration phase was started.
- Integration and commissioning occurred in MARCH 2001.

The HFBSS was be available for aircraft testing starting in April 2001.

The field mapping data of the system actual performance for comparison to the predicted performance, along with lessons learned from the integration efforts will be provided in a future paper.

We have learned from our past high power RF systems such as EMEGS to develop a manual process for operation first. Therefore, a period of one year is planned for manual (semi-automated) operation. Then, in the following year, we will add automation to areas such as field calibration and automated testing based on the year of manual operation.

Conclusions

The HFBSS is a new aircraft ground test facility that simulate the world wide HF Broadcast EME encountered by airborne aircraft. A novel antenna design that provides both vertical and horizontal polarization from a single portable V dipole curtain antenna. The antenna is driven by a 300 KW, class D transmitter. After integration and commissioning in March 2001 the system will be used for aircraft ground electromagnetic compatibly testing with HF Broadcast EME by the NAVAIRWARCENACDIV.

References

[1] NAWCAD Report NAWCADPAX—98-156-TM, High Intensity Radiated Field External Environments for Civil Aircraft Operating in the United States of America, 12 November 1998,